

DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONAL QUALITIES OF ADOLESCENT SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract: This article presents the socio-psychological foundations of the formation of personal qualities in adolescent schoolchildren, as well as psychological and pedagogical information about the improvement of personal qualities in the development of adolescents through the implementation of communicative processes corresponding to their age characteristics.

Keywords:... person, personality, adolescence, development, progress, behavior, socialization, crisis, communication, education, activity, objective, subjective, status, education, work.

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Abstract: В данной статье представлены социально-психологические основы формирования личностных качеств у школьников-подростков, а также приведены психолого-педагогические сведения о совершенствовании личностных качеств в развитии подростков посредством реализации коммуникативных процессов, соответствующих их возрастным особенностям.

Keywords:... человек, личность, подростковый возраст, развитие, прогресс, поведение, социализация, кризис, общение, образование, деятельность, объективный, субъективный, статус, образование, работа

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An important psychological moment in describing a person as a character is his dynamic characteristics, which are characterized by his status in society (economic, political, legal, ideological basis, i.e. his place in society, prestige, position). There is always a system of continuous interaction. The social function of the group and the role in the family and community, which is associated with group activities and life, the profession that a person must perform, its orientation towards a specific goal, values, spirituality, activates the personality. It is able to participate in all aspects. Status, role, value orientation are the main traits, qualities and attributes of a person, which serve as the basis for his structure. (from simple stereotypes to examples of folk wisdom). The secondary symptoms of its composition are in the form of signs. Human character and inclinations manifest themselves very effectively, combining the interaction of primary and secondary personality traits. The main form that develops, improves and stabilizes a person's personal qualities is his way of life, which leaves a certain mark on society and social biography. Serving a person to his people can raise his respect in society, and he can also become a national treasure. [1-116].

One of the main characteristics of a person as a subject of activity is his productive consciousness of development in this area (as a reflection of objective activity and as a modifier of reality). A person, as a subject of practical activity, not only describes his personal qualities and attributes, but also acts as a technical means and technology of labor. Practical activity is viewed as part of a universal and individual experience, as the use of acquired, learned and solid experience. A person who is the subject of theoretical activity is characterized by his knowledge, professional skills, mental abilities, which are directly related to a certain system of symptoms. As a result of the growth of the mental activity of the individual, news and laws arise that can become the driving force behind the development of society. The relationship between the products of ancestral heritage and the potential of generations requires a combination of theoretical and practical activities, although both types of activities are characterized by creativity, productivity and the development of science and technology. When an activity is closely associated with experimentation, its effectiveness, purposefulness, and feasibility are increased to a higher level.

Adolescence is the period of study in schools and other educational institutions. The leading activity of this period is educational activity in which the child undergoes significant changes as a person, in addition to acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities related to learning. Adolescence is one of the most difficult and important stages of development. The primary adolescent period is 11-13 years old, and the secondary period is 14-15 years old. The most important feature of this period is that it is the period of transition from childhood to adolescence, from adolescence to maturity. [3-72]

However, as noted above, adolescence is a time of conflict. Some scientists also call this a period of "crises, recessions". The reason is that there are so many crises in the child's psyche that he wants to resolve this crisis on the one hand, and on the other, he lacks the ability, strength and intelligence to solve it. For example, one of the factors that gets in the way of "feeling great" is their financial dependence on their parents. As spiritual as they are, teenagers go to school and ask their parents for money, and they treat them like a child and give them little money. Second, they don't want to be like adults. For example, if girls try on their mothers' clothes or boys try on their fathers' clothes in front of a mirror, they immediately notice that they are not suitable for them. In addition, the disadvantages of appearance, i.e. unpleasant rashes on the face and body cause negative emotions in him. All of this can lead to emotional turmoil during adolescence. But, despite this, the child consciously or unconsciously seeks to develop his mental abilities, longs for beautiful thinking, and this is the most important change in his mental development.

Self-awareness is important for the development of the personality of adolescents. They affect the adolescent's mental world, mental performance, and attitude to the environment.

Psychological research shows that most adolescents have a correct understanding of spiritual and moral concepts such as determination, humility, pride, sincerity, kindness, compassion, and justice. As a result of the assimilation of the foundations of science in their life experience, stable beliefs and scientific worldviews are formed, on the basis of which moral ideals begin to form. The ideals of adolescents are based on dreams, goals and plans. There is passion and interest in a particular profession. Dreams are very different from each other.

The study of teenage communication showed that they have different moral concepts. A.I.Maliovanov divides adolescents into four groups: 1) adolescents who act on the basis of positive rules of behavior that they understand, whose words and actions are appropriate; 2) adolescents whose moral ideas correspond to their actions; 3) adolescents whose behavior is characterized by knowledge of moral norms that do not act in accordance with this knowledge; 4) Adolescents who do not understand the connection between the moral requirements they know and their daily behavior.

Scientific research and life experience have shown that adolescents who misunderstand certain ethical concepts, misjudge certain personality traits, strive for independence and try to demonstrate their will, try to cultivate negative qualities in themselves. They even try to lose the formed positive qualities. The main task of teachers and parents is to destroy their misconceptions and prevent adolescents from going astray. [2]

There are two aspects of the development of a teenager as a person: on the one hand, the desire to be in close contact with others, peers, submission to group norms, and on the other hand, some difficulties in the inner world of the child due to increased independence. There are also contradictions between understanding others and self-awareness. Teens often overestimate their potential, while others are skeptical of their strength, will, and potential. But even in this case, they strive to gain recognition at least in the peer community, and communication with them becomes the meaning of life. If during this period a teenager is rejected by his peers for some reason, he will regard it as a very tragic event: refusal from school and even suicide.

The surest and most effective way to prevent the difficulties of adolescence is to achieve a steady interest in something, to make the motives of activity more meaningful. For example, it is of great pedagogical importance to create conditions for satisfying the interest of a child who is interested in technologies during this period, so that they do not become useless, to encourage every action, to treat him as a capable person. Knowing your interests and setting new goals is the basis for

the development of a child's personality. Only then will his perception of his "I" be positive, his self-esteem objective and fair, and he will have a good idea of what he is capable of and who he is. [3]

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